

EFFECT OF EXTERNAL DEBT ON MILITARY EXPENDITURE IN NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20124379>

Keywords

*External Debt,
Military
Expenditure,
Debt Servicing,
Budget
Balance*

Abstract: *This study examined the effect of external debt on military expenditure in Nigeria using annual time series data spanning from 2000 to 2024. The study was motivated by the rising level of insecurity in Nigeria and the increasing dependence on external borrowing to finance military operations and other government obligations. Secondary data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), World Development Indicators (WDI), and Debt Management Office (DMO). Military expenditure was modeled as a function of external debt, debt servicing, and budget balance within the framework of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. Preliminary tests using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test revealed a mixed order of integration among the variables, thereby justifying the use of the ARDL approach. The Bounds cointegration test confirmed the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables. The empirical findings indicated that external debt had a negative and statistically significant effect on military expenditure in Nigeria in the long run, while debt servicing and budget balance exhibited negative but insignificant relationships with military expenditure. The error correction mechanism showed that deviations from short-run equilibrium were corrected at a speed of 56.6% annually. Diagnostic tests further confirmed the absence of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity, while the stability test revealed that the model was stable over the study period. The study concluded that excessive external borrowing undermines the government’s capacity to sustainably finance military expenditure and maintain national security. Consequently, the study recommended prudent debt management, fiscal discipline, and efficient allocation of budgetary resources toward security and developmental needs in Nigeria.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Most developing countries like Nigeria has resorted to external borrowing in order to bridge domestic resource gap. The economic

Godstime Ikechukwu, Ogu Callistus Opara and Mbata Michael .N.

thought here is that in line Keynesian economics, public expenditure triggers economic growth through aggregate demand. However, it has been often argued that when a borrowing nation channels appropriately the borrowed resources into productive investment; this will no doubt incur capital and recurrent expenditure that will embolden growth and development. However, economic growth cannot occur in a vacuum- it occurs in a stable economic environment for both the domestic actors and foreign investors. It is because of this why most governments provide adequate security measures to ensure that the environment supports growth with safety of human and material capacity (Ashraf and Chaudhary, 2008).

Nigeria has been facing the problem of insecurity over the years and this has led to external borrowing over the years, with series of rescheduling debt, amortization and debt servicing. The costs of the external borrowing has been transmitted to the economy and affected the capacity of the government to provide the basic necessities for the citizenry; hence, the provision of security has been affected as a result. Thus, to mitigate this effect, the Nigerian government resorts to borrowing. Borrowing for the provision of security means no direct harm, but excessive foreign debt accumulation may be the reason for lopsided domestic growth and foreign capital inflow. Prior to now, Nigeria wasn't suffering the problem of huge external debt burden, but the current trend seems to be external borrowing.

For instance, the volume of debt rose from \$32bn in 2015 to \$54bn in 2019 (DMO, 2020). The empirical investigation and economic import of this rising debt on military expenditure is that insecurity would be poorly handled due lack of the necessary wherewithal to fund the military to face the challenge head on. Hence, borrowing ensues and this triggers the rate of borrowing when the budget expectations are below the oil price bench mark. Unfortunately, in Nigeria, most debts repayment have been rescheduled repeatedly, with the effect of a continuous debt increase that is virtually unabated. In countries with large military outlay, the role of military spending in relation to external debt is important. Obviously, borrowing to finance military expenditure might constitutes a drag on economic growth and military expenditure, especially for the less developed nations of Africa like Nigeria that are characterized with series of political and religious crises, macro-economic instability and high level of insecurity. The volume of military budgetary allocation continues to increase rapidly such that the country spends an important portion of its external borrowed fund on defence at the expense of productive sectors like manufacturing, agriculture, construction, health and education. The continued large military outlay in the 3face of high debt burden may have some potential adverse economic effects on the growth performance of a nation, but the obligation of the government to military operation remains an issue. Hence, it has been debated that the external debt for military

expenditure purposes bears a positive external effect; while others argue the converse. Thus, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between external debt burden and military spending in Nigeria between to lend empirical evidence on the subject.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Over the years the volume of military budgetary allocation has increased rapidly such that it has been argued that the allocation crowds out important sectors of the economy. Prior to this time, military expenditure in the budget was not heavily budgeted for, but the increasing spate of violence and insecurity has caused the budget to be reviewed to cater for dynamic nature of violence and terrorism. Military expenditure is a function of the budget and national income, however; when the national income falls short of its estimates reflected in the budget balance, it poses a challenge to the government in carrying out its function; hence, resorts to borrowing which bears its concomitant effects on the economy in the long run. These effects could be positive if the borrowing produces the right results and is settled duly or it could produce a negative effect if it falls short of expectations and serviced constantly at the peril of the economy. Thus, the continued large military outlay in the face of high debt burden may have some potential adverse economic effects on the performance of the Nigerian economy. However, with the state of the economy and series of external debt problems faced by the country; can it be said that there is no effect of debt burden on military expenditure to combat insecurity in the

country? What are the effects of external borrowing on military expenditure? Furthermore is the external borrowing justified on the grounds of provision of military services for security purposes? Although the issue of borrowing for military protection remains debatable due to its impact on the economy; hence, this study will carry out an empirical investigation to lend empirical evidence on the issue.

1.3. Objectives of the Study.

The specific objective of this study are as follows:

- i. To ascertain the extent to which external debt affects military expenditure in Nigeria;
- iii. To find out the extent to which debt servicing affects military expenditure in Nigeria; and lastly
- iii. To find out the extent to which budget balance affects military expenditure in Nigeria.

1.4. Research Questions.

The specific questions that will guide this study are as follows:

- i. To what extent has external debt affected the military expenditure of Nigeria?
- ii. How has debt servicing affected the military expenditure of Nigeria?
- iii. To what extent does budget balance affect military expenditure of Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypotheses.

The following research hypotheses will guide this study:

- i. **Ho:** There is no significant relationship between external debt and military expenditure in Nigeria;

ii. **Ho:** There is no significant relationship between debt servicing and military expenditure in Nigeria;

iii. **Ho:** There is no significant relationship between budget balance and military expenditure of Nigeria;

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study is centered on external debt and military expenditure in Nigeria. It is based on secondary data with a time period of 25 years i.e.2000-2024. The time series period chosen for this study was adduced to adequately capture military spending in the military and civilian administrations in Nigeria. This is because the time periods sufficiently reflect the gamut of experience Nigeria has had with military operations. The ambit of this study is within quantitative analysis and thus, focuses on five key variables being external debt, debt servicing, budget balance and military expenditure which aided model formulation for econometric measurement and analysis of short run and long run effects.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The study will be of immense benefit to policy makers and institutions as it seeks to establish the theoretical connection between external debt and military expenditure in Nigeria with the aid of the Neo-patrimonial theory. Furthermore, it will present an opportunity to empirically assess other literatures on external debt and military expenditure in Nigeria. This will bring forth the empirical underpinning of each study and how it connects with the scope of the study; for instance, it will examine the empirical links between the study and the

selected variables such as external debt, debt servicing, budget balance and their link with military spending. Previous studies will form the bedrock for model formulation and estimation that will aid in lending empirical evidence to the topic. In addition, it will be of immense enlightenment to researchers as it would broaden the view of the research subject by opening it up for criticism and further researches through identified gaps in the literature.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1 External debt

External debt refers to the borrowings of government from foreign countries to finance infrastructural development due to the insufficiency of their own resources. In Nigeria it has become a frequent phenomenon for government to borrow money when it wills without putting into considering some macroeconomic factors and state of the nation. This is despite the annual budget on capital expenditure and revenue. According to the Debt Management Office (2005), the Nigerian government like most oil producing countries started borrowing after the oil boom in 1970 in order to overcome the short fall in the provision of basic services resulting from reduction in foreign exchange earnings during the boom. It became an increasing phenomenon by successive government justifiably and sometimes not justifiable Al-Fawaz (2016) stated that external debt is a global phenomenon that is acceptable to a certain extent and under certain controls. If it exceeds

certain limit and goes out of these controls, it would have a negative effects on GDP and sustainable development of a country. Based on external debt report, the outstanding external public debt rose during the democratic regime especially in the present administration from \$29bn in 1999 to \$54bn in 2019. In 2010 the external debt was \$21bn, in 2015 it was \$32 and rose to \$43bn in 2017 which is 25.6% increase from 2016. In 2018 alone it was \$50bn which was 16.81% increase from 2016 (DMO, 2020).

2.1.2 Military expenditure and external debt nexus

Nigeria is a developing nation and conflict assumed different dimensions accounting for large volume of defence expenditure with an attendant increase in external debt. Defence spending continued to increase even with the series of agitations for defence spending cut. The aggregate defence spending in 1986 was N951.4 million. The total foreign debt in 1986 stood at N41452.4 billion and the debt servicing ratio was N1631.59 billion. The defence spending as a ratio of external debt was 2.30 percent indicating that large percentage of the external debt went to defence sector in 1986. In 1990 total defence expenditure rose to N1606.9 billion with total external debt at N298614.4 billion. The rise in defence spending was triggered by Nigeria's active participation in West African regional peace keeping particularly in Liberia and coup d'état in 1990. However, defence expenditure burden on external debt stood at 0.54 per cent. Increase in defence spending continued unabated and in

1999 defence spending reached a peak of N580117.74 billion and foreign debt increased to N633017.0 billion. This was due to the general election in the country in 1999. In Nigeria, election periods are seriously mare with violence, power tussles, wanton destruction of lives and properties, hence the need to increase defence spending. Irrespective of the country's external reserve, foreign borrowing sustained a tremendous increase within this period. Between 2000 and 2011 Nigeria witnessed a growing democratic state accompanied with series of internal crises which sustained increase in defence spending. As at 2004 total defence spending and external borrowing stood at N76057.3 billion and N4890269.6 billion respectively. The surge in defence spending was also accompanied by increase kidnapping of indigenes and foreigners, ethnic and religious violence across the northern and southern part of the country. However, the defence expenditure burden on external debt was highest in 2005 when it was 4.15 per cent, thereafter it declined steadily to 3.08 per cent and 0.39 per cent in 2008 and 2011 respectively. By 2011 kidnapping of both foreigners and indigenes increased tremendously in the Southern states of Enugu, Anambra, Rivers, Ebonyi, Bayelsa and Abia states, whereas the Northern states of Bauchi, Plateau, Kano and Kaduna, Yobe, Borno and Niger and Federal Capital Territory – Abuja, the Islamic extremist sect– Boko Haram unleashed series of attack on Churches, both private enterprises and government installation, leading to a wanton destruction

Godstime Ikechukwu, Ogu Callistus Opara and Mbata Michael .N.

lives and properties. Aggregate defence spending in 2010 was N86029 billion, while the total external debt stood at N6898450 billion. The table below shows the increasing rate of

external debt in relation to military expenditure in the country.

Fig. i: External debt and military expenditure from 2000-2024.

From the table above, it can be seen that external debt has been surreptitiously rising far above the expenditure allocation of military expenditure, with its peak around 2015 during the Goodluck Jonathan administration when it was heavily budgeted for leading to contracts

for arms supply which were diverted in the process.

Table ii below shows the relationship between debt servicing and military expenditure in the country. From the table it can be seen that the incidence of debt servicing has been on the increase.

Fig. ii: Debt servicing and military expenditure from 2000-2024.

From the table above, the debt service ratio was at its peak around the year 2000 and continued to decline till its all-time-low around 2007,

when the Obasanjo’s administration secured debt relief and cancellation for the economy.

Thereafter, the case has been different as debt servicing continues to rise.

Fig iii: Military expenditure and budget balance from 2000-2024.

From the table above, it can be seen that the budget balance is clearly below the military expenditure line; indicating a steady increase in military expenditure over the budget and financed through external borrowing.

2.2 Theoretical review: The Neo-patrimonial theory

This theoretical framework provides a powerful lens for understanding Nigeria's deeply entrenched relationship between corruption and counterinsurgency financing. This theoretical framework is rooted in Weber's (1968) concept of patrimonialism, which describes a system where governance and leadership rely on personal loyalty and hierarchical patronage rather than institutionalized rules. Neo-patrimonialism expands on this by reflecting the fusion of public and private spheres within governance systems, where state resources are often privatized for the personal benefit of ruling

elites (Eisenstadt, 1973; Bratton & van de Walle, 1999). This approach underscores systemic practices such as clientelism, nepotism, and resource misappropriation, particularly prevalent in many African states, including Nigeria (Anders, 2005; Olaniyan, 2015). In the Nigerian context, neo-patrimonialism manifests in the weakening of formal state institutions due to their overlap with informal networks of patronage. These networks often operate to benefit a few at the expense of the broader population, promoting corruption and mediocrity while eroding meritocracy and institutional efficiency (Nkwede, 2015). Thus, from the foregoing, one can see that this theory is apt for this study as it explains the nexus between the blending of formal and informal governance as it undermines accountability and transparency, creating an environment conducive to the mismanagement of public resources. Neo-

Godstime Ikechukwu, Ogu Callistus Opara and Mbata Michael .N.

patrimonialism thus serves as a crucial framework for examining how governance failures, especially those rooted in corruption and resource mismanagement, have exacerbated the escalation insecurity in Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Review

There are few literatures on the nexus between corruption and military expenditure that are empirically based; however, some of them are examined in details as follows: Shimawua (2020) assessed the military campaign against Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria. This study examined the extent to which corruption has affected military operations in the fight. Data was obtained from secondary materials which include books, journals, periodicals, newspapers, and the internet. Data analysis was done using the technique of content analysis. Findings revealed that the fight against Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria has lasted so long due to corruption that has eaten deep into the fabrics of the military hierarchy, and that this has significantly affected the fortunes of the military in the Boko Haram fight.

Duruji (2018), examined the military's budget against the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria covering the period of 2009-2017. The study found that there were shortfalls with respect to monies budgeted for the war and what has been achieved so far, stating that the expenditures were not commensurate to what has been achieved in the war, thus advocating for prudence in managing military budget against insurgency in the country.

Usman (2017), assessed the impact of corruption in the military's fight against insurgency in the north eastern region of Nigeria covering 2009-2015. The study employed secondary data and adopted content and observational method of analysis. It discovered that the failure of the Nigerian military to defeat insurgents in the country was due to corruption perpetrated by highly placed government functionaries, thus advocating for the continued war against corruption.

Akume & Godswill (2016) analyzed the challenge of managing insurgency in Nigeria spanning 2009 to 2015. The study used documentary research method to examine why government is unable to contain the menace of insurgency. The paper discovered that government agencies' opportunistic behavior accounts for the poor performance of government in wiping out insurgency. The study pointed at large scale corruption as the reason for the poor performance of Nigeria's military forces.

Suleiman & Aminu (2015), in their study examined how the cycle of bad governance and corruption have affected the fight against the Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria. The study examined the cycle of bad governance and corruption particularly in military expenditure in Nigeria's north-east fight against the insurgents. Qualitative data were employed through interviews. The study found that the war has not been fairly fought, concluding that corruption has affected the successes of the Nigerian forces, thereby prolonging the military's campaign against the insurgency.

Godstime Ikechukwu, Ogu Callistus Opara and Mbata Michael .N.

2.4 Gap in the Study

There exists few empirical literature on corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria. Furthermore, most of the studies were carried out using descriptive analysis, (Akume and Godswill (2016); Shimawua (2020); with recourse to few studies like Suleiman and Aminu (2015) that were quantitatively analyzed. The empirical works reviewed above were mostly qualitative in analysis; however, this study models military expenditure as a function of corruption and other control variables such as budgetary financial management, quality of public administration and macro-economic environment. These variables thereby close the gap in previous studies and using a time period of 1990-2023 brings the study to a more recent period to make room for lending empirical evidence to support or refute the impact of corruption on military expenditure in Nigeria.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This research study utilized Ex-post facto research design to investigate “The effect of external debt on military expenditure in Nigeria: (2000-2024)”. Ex-post facto is a research after the facto has been known and it applies to secondary data (Anyanwu, 2000). Based on the nature of this research study, secondary data was employed.

3.2 Source of Data

The data for this study was obtained from the World Development Indicators of The World Bank (2023).

3.3. Model Specification

Godstime Ikechukwu, Ogu Callistus Opara and Mbata Michael .N.

In an attempt to investigate “The effect of external debt on economic growth of the Nigerian economy: (2000-2024)”, the work of Alexander, Hellen & Ahmed (2014) on “Military Spending and External Debt Burden in Nigeria.. The studied utilized secondary data using real external debt, total military expenditure, gross fixed capital formation which is a proxy for investment, real gross domestic product and debt service ratio. The study applied Granger causality, vector autoregressive, variance decomposition and impulse response techniques. The outcome of the results showed long run and a unidirectional causal relationship between military spending and external debt.

However, this study makes an improvement over their analysis by focusing on mainly the fiscal components of external debt and military spending which is shown in the model below:

$$\text{MILEXP} = f(\text{EXTDEBT}, \text{DEBTSER}, \text{BUDGBAL})$$

In econometric form:

$$\text{MILEXP} = b_0 + b_1 \text{EXTDEBT} + b_2 \text{DEBTSER} + b_3 \text{BUDGBAL} + \mu$$

Thus; the model variables are defined as follows:

MILEXP= military expenditure.

EXTDEBT= External debt.

DEBTSER=Debt servicing as a percentage of gross domestic product.

BUDGBAL= Budget balance.

$b_1 - b_3$ are coefficients of parameters estimates and b_0 is the intercept of the model. μ is the white noise error term. It is expected that $b_1 < 0$, $b_2 < 0$ and $b_3 > 0$ as our *a priori* expectations.

3.4. Pre-Estimation Tests

3.4.1 Unit Root Test

This was to test for the stationarity of the time series data. Test for stationarity was done to avoid the problem of spurious regression. The Augmented Dickey-fuller test statistic was in this regard. The augmentation in the fuller test is to resolve issues that may arise from serial correlation in the model. The essence of unit root testing is to avoid the problem of spurious regression i.e. not having the sample variables oscillating about a mean value. If the sample variables wander off significantly from their mean values, there might be stationarity issues and the estimation technique might be flawed as well. The unit root test plays an important role in data analysis because it determines the method of estimation of the parameter estimates to be employed. The null and alternative hypothesis for the unit root test are summarized below:

H₀: There is a unit root in the model.

H₁: There is no unit root in the model.

Decision rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the Prob.F-test statistic exceeds the 5% critical value, except otherwise.

3.4.2 Cointegration Test: Bounds test.

The ARDL form for cointegration (Bounds test) states that if F-statistics is greater than I(0) and I(1) bounds, it means there is evidence of long run relationship in the model.

To perform the ARDL Bounds test, 5 cointegration tests are carried out and the hypotheses are stated as follows:

H₀: $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = 0$

H₁: $\beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq 0$

If there is no evidence of cointegration, the error correction model (ECM) representation of the model will be estimated.

3.4.3 Normality Test

This was used to test whether the error terms were normally distributed. The normality test adopted for this study was the Jargue–Bera (JB) statistics which follows a chi-square distribution. If the prob. value of Jargue–Bera (JB) is less 5% level of significance, then the error term is not normally, but if otherwise, we accept the normality assumption.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was used for the model estimation.

3.6 Test of Significance

This was to test whether the variables were significant at 5% level of significance individually and jointly. To do this, the t-test was employed to test each of the variables. Stating in terms of null and alternative hypothesis we had:

H₀: $\beta_i = 0$, where $i = 1-3$ and

H₁: $\beta_i \neq 0$

Decision rule: Accept H₀ if $t_{cal} < t_{tab}$ at $\alpha = 0.05$, otherwise reject H₀. alternatively, accept H₀ if prob. value > 0.05 , otherwise, reject H₀. On the other hand, the joint test hypothesis is stated as follows:

H₀: $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = 0$; and

H₁: $\beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq 0$

Decision rule: Accept H₀ if prob. value > 0.05 , otherwise reject H₀.

3.7 Post-Estimation Test

3.7.1 Test for Autocorrelation

The classical assumption has it that the error terms of observations do not correlate is the error term of one observation does not influence another. To detect this malady, the Breusch-Godfrey test was used.

Decision rule: Accept H_0 if prob.value > 0.05, otherwise reject H_0 .

3.7.2 Test for Heteroscedasticity

The classical assumption has it that the error terms of observations have constant variance; otherwise, non-constant variance and this could create problems in the model estimation which is undesirable and violates the classical assumption of constant variance. To detect this malady, the researcher employed the Breusch-Godfrey-Pagan heteroscedasticity test which follows a chi-square distribution.

Decision rule: If chi-square F- prob.value > 0.05, it means that there is no serial correlation in the model, except otherwise.

3.7.3 Goodness of Fit of the Model

The adjusted R-squared was examined to test for the Goodness of fit of the model. It explains how much variation in the model was accounted for by the explanatory variables of the model. A value above from 50% and above shows a good fit of the model; except below.

3.7.4 Model Stability

This test is to determine the stability of the model. If the cumulative sum of squares of the residual lie within the 5% bands, it means the model is stable except otherwise.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1: Military expenditure (MILEXP), Budgetary balance (BUDGBAL), External Debt (EXTDEBT) and Debt service (DEBTSER) from 2000-2023.

YEAR	DEBTSER (%)	EXTDEBT(N' Bill)	BUDGBAL(N' Bil l)	GDP(N' Bill)	MILEXP(N' Bill)
2000	56.6	67.82	4.07	7062.75	0.5
2001	53.1	73.13	-3.22	8234.49	0.8
2002	43.27	93.98	1.34	11501.45	1
2003	42.09	192.94	-2.2	13556.97	0.6
2004	35.49	130.35	5.49	18124.06	0.5
2005	18.94	169.65	4.91	23121.85	0.4
2006	9.4	222.79	8.76	30375.18	0.3
2007	8.12	266.33	-1.12	34675.94	0.4
2008	7.28	335.38	5.7	39954.21	0.5
2009	8.62	302.46	-5.33	43461.46	0.5
2010	9.39	374.1	-4.17	55469.35	0.5
2011	17.43	419.94	0.43	63713.36	0.6
2012	17.38	467.16	-0.13	72599.63	0.5

2013	18.29	521.86	-2.66	81009.96	0.5
2014	18.16	576	-2.43	90136.98	0.4
2015	21.02	494.31	-3.8	95177.74	0.4
2016	24.47	405.02	-4.64	102575.4	0.4
2017	25.36	375.76	-5.42	114899.3	0.4
2018	28.7	421.74	-4.32	145639.1	0.5
2019	30.19	474.52	-4.66	154252.5	0.5
2020	35.63	441.07	-5.58	145639.1	0.6
2021	36.79	441.07	-5.48	176075.5	1
2022	40.44	476.47	-5.42	202365	0.7
2023	48.67	363.82	-4.19	596100	0.8
2024	52.9	187.64	-3.27	608875	1.1

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin (2024) and Statistica.com (2024)

4.2 Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.2.1 Pre-Estimation Test: Unit Root, Specification Error Test, Cointegration and Normality Test.

Table 4.2.1: Unit Root Test Summary: Augmented Dickey-Fuller test.

VARIABLE	ADF (LEVEL)	5% CRITICAL	ADF(1 ST DIFF)	5% CRITICAL	REMARK
EXTDEBT	-3.296350	-2.954021	7.343417*	-2.9571110	I(0)
DEBTSER	-1.119951	-2.954201	-5.63069*	-2.9571110	I(1)
BUDGBAL	-0.980574	-2.954201	-5.654563	-2.9571110	I(1)
MILEXP	-1.231448	-2.954201	-5.55626*	-2.9571110	I(1)

The Asterisks (*) is used to indicate stationarity at the 5% level of significance. Source: Author’s computation with E-views 10 package.

The unit root test above revealed that MILEXP, BUDGBAL, DEBTSER were was found to be stationary at first difference I (1), while EXTDEBT was stationary at level i.e I(0), which implies that the variables have a mixed order of integration; therefore apt for the application of

4.2.1 Test for Unit Root

The test for unit root was carried with the Augmented Dickey fuller test. The summary is shown below:

an ARDL test in analyzing the short run and the long run relationship in the model.

4.2.1 Cointegration Test: ARDL Bounds Test

H₀: There is a long run relationship in the model.

H₁: There is a long run relationship in the model.

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	6.364142	10%	3.47	4.45
k	3	5%	4.01	5.07
		2.5%	4.52	5.62
		1%	5.17	6.36

Source: Author’s Computation with E-views 10

From table 4.3 above, the F-statistics for the model is 6.36414 and is greater than the upper I(0) and I(1) bounds of 4.01 and 5.07 respectively at 5% level of significance. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is presence of cointegration in the model.

This implies that there is a long run relationship between corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria. Since there is a long run relationship, we therefore estimate the short run and long run ARDL regression models.

4.2 Model Estimation.

Table 4.2.1: ARDL Cointegrating and Long Run Form

Conditional Error Correction Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.299864	0.658651	3.491780	0.0026
@TREND	0.022999	0.007242	3.175811	0.0052
MILEXP(-1)*	-0.566895	0.182798	-3.101199	0.0062
LNDEBTSER**	-0.128219	0.177357	-0.722945	0.4790
LNEXTDEBT**	-0.825278	0.222310	-3.712289	0.0016
LNBUDGBAL**	-0.210539	0.101532	-2.073630	0.0527

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNDEBTSER	-0.226178	0.353318	-0.640155	0.5301
LNEXTDEBT	-1.455787	0.624949	-2.329450	0.0317
LNBUDGBAL	-0.371391	0.215148	-1.726209	0.1014

EC = MILEXP - (-0.2262*LNDEBTSER -1.4558*LNEXTDEBT -0.3714 *LNBUDGBAL)

ECM Regression

Case 5: Unrestricted Constant and Unrestricted Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	
C	2.299864	0.431439	5.330685	0.0000	
@TREND	0.022999	0.004799	4.792122	0.0001	
CointEq(-1)*	-0.566895	0.104023	-5.449709	0.0000	
R-squared	0.601373	Mean dependent var		0.025000	
Adjusted R-squared	0.563408	S.D. dependent var		0.177544	
S.E. of regression	0.117312	Akaike info criterion		-1.331489	signi
Sum squared resid	0.289005	Schwarz criterion		-1.184233	fican
Log likelihood	18.97787	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.292422	ce.
F-statistic	15.84041	Durbin-Watson stat		2.211357	Henc
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000064				e;

Short run analysis:

From the short run result above, it can be seen that EXTDEBT, DEBTSER, BUDGBAL were all insignificant at 5% level of significance. The ECM coefficient was negative and significant at the 5% level of significance; hence, any short run dis-equilibrium in the model will be corrected at the rate of 56.6% per annum and this will take less than 2 years.

Long Run Analysis:

EXTDEBT: has a negative and significant relationship with MILEXP at 5% level of significance. Hence; external debt has a significant effect on military expenditure in Nigeria in the long run.

DEBTSERV: has a negative and insignificant relationship with MILEXP at 5% level of significance. Hence; debt servicing has an insignificant effect on military expenditure in Nigeria in the long run.

BUDGBAL: has a negative and insignificant relationship with MILEXP at 5% level of

et balance has an insignificant effect on military spending in Nigeria in the long run.

4.3 Test of Significance.

4.3. 1 Individual Test of Significance.

I. DEBTSER

H₀: DEBTSER has no significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at α=0.05

H₁: DEBTSER has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at α=0.05

Prob.value =0.5301 α = 0.05

Decision: Since the prob.value (0.5301) > 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that debt servicing has no significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at α=0.05

ii. EXTDEBT

H₀: EXTDEBT has no significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at α=0.05

H₁: EXTDEBT has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at α=0.05

Prob.value =0.0317 α = 0.05

Decision: Since the prob.value (0.0317) < 0.05 the null hypothesis rejected and it is concluded thaexternal debt has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha=0.05$

iii. BUDGBAL

H₀: BUDGBAL has no significant relationship with military spending in Nigeria at $\alpha=0.05$

H₁: BUDGBAL has a significant relationship with military spending in Nigeria at $\alpha=0.05$

Prob.value = 0.1014 $\alpha = 0.05$

Decision: Since the prob.value (0.1014) > 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that budget balance has a significant relationship with military spending in Nigeria at $\alpha=0.05$

4.3.2 Joint Test of Significance (ANOVA).

F-statistic	0.316516	Prob. F(2,16)	0.7331
Obs*R-squared	0.913409	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.6334

Decision: Since the observed Prob. Chi-square value is greater than 0.05, it means that there is no serial correlation in the model.

4.4.2 Breusch-Godfrey Test for Heteroscedasticity.

F-statistic	0.161966	Prob. F(5,18)	0.9733
Obs*R-squared	1.033284	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.9598
Scaled explained SS	1.144858	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.9501

Decision: Since the Prob. Chi-square value (0.9773) is greater than 0.05, it means that there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity in the model.

4.4.3 Test for Causality

H₀: EXTDEBT=DEBTSER=BUDGBAL=0

H₁: EXTDEBT≠DEBTSER≠BUDGBAL≠0

Decision: From the regression result, the F-prob. value is 0.000135 which is less than 0.05; hence we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a joint impact of EXTDEBT, DEBTSER and BUDGAL on military expenditure in Nigeria at 5% level of significance.

4.4 Post Estimation Tests

4.4.1 Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test.

H₀: There is no serial autocorrelation in the model at $\alpha = 0.05$.

H₁: There is presence of serial autocorrelation in the model at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

H₀: There is no heteroscedasticity in the model at $\alpha = 0.05$.

H₁: There is presence of heteroscedasticity in the model at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

H₀: There is no causality between government debt growth rate and economic growth of Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$.

H₁: There is causality between government debt growth rate and economic growth of Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Decision: From the Granger causality test result, it was seen that causality exists and flowed uni-directionally from BUDGBAL DEBTSER. From the causality test, it can be seen that there is no direct causality between external debt and military expenditure, but between other control variables in the model (See appendix for table).

4.4.4 Goodness of Fit of the Model.

4.4.5. Model Stability

Since the residual line lies between the 5% boundary lines, it means the model is stable.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

EXTDEBT was negatively related to military expenditure and statistically significant at 5% level of significance in the long run. The negative relationship conforms to our a priori expectation. The significant relationship it bears with military expenditure is suggestive of the fact that the effect of external debt erodes the capacity of government to provide the security needed for developmental effects in the country.

DEBTSER was negatively related to military expenditure and statistically insignificant at 5% level of significance in the long run. The negative relationship conforms to our a priori expectation. The result of the findings suggests

$$\text{Adj.}R^2 = 0.651482 \times 100\% = 65.14\%$$

From the result of the regression, the Adjusted R-squared shows that about 65.14% variation in military expenditure can be explained by the explanatory variables; hence, the model has a very strong explanatory power in relation to military expenditure in Nigeria.

4.4.5. Model Stability

that the government should put up more fiscal responsibility in managing its budget i.e. financial probity is required to avoid depleting the external reserves in an attempt to provide security services. Thus, the debt management office (DMO), needs to carefully management its debt obligations in order not to defeat the purpose of securing external debt for security service provision.

BUDGBAL was negatively related to military expenditure and statistically insignificant at 5% level of significance in the long run. The positive relationship conforms to our a priori expectation. This research finding is supportive of the fact that the budget remains a veritable fiscal tool in meeting up with economic plans of the country. This invariably means the budget should be managed in order not to record huge

deficits which could trigger borrowing from international creditors ; thus, leading to the possibility of debt servicing and economic problems in the long run.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study examined corruption on military expenditure in Nigeria for a 34-year period (1990-2023). The following summarizes the findings of the research;

- i. External debt has a significant effect on military expenditure in Nigeria;
- ii. There is a joint impact of external debt, debt servicing and budget balance on military expenditure in Nigeria; and lastly
- iii. There is no direct causality between external debt and military expenditure in Nigeria

5.2 Conclusion

The findings showed that external debt, debt servicing and budget balance had a significant impact on military expenditure in Nigeria in the long run. Even though there was no direct causality between external debt and military expenditure in Nigeria, it was shown that the control variables-debt servicing and budget balance were significant in the outcome of the analysis; hence, further validating the joint test of significance. Based on evidence from the above findings, it was concluded that external debt has a significant effect on military expenditure in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

From the findings of the study the following recommendations were made. They are as follows:

- i. A major policy implication of this result is that concerted effort should be made by the government to curtail external borrowing from foreign creditors. By so doing the country will be able to conserve its foreign reserves as well as save its financial resources and put it to best uses for developmental purposes such as maintaining law and order, national security etc.
- ii. Again, the government should ensure probity in the use and management of its appropriation budget so as to ensure maximum impact of fiscal policy from the stand point of budget provisions as a stabilization tool in the economy.
- iii. Lastly, the government should develops ways and means to settle its debt obligations rather than resorting to debt servicing which mounts pressure on the economy and also affects the fiscal , social and welfare plans of the country in the long run.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies.

A VAR analysis will be adequate to capture the interaction between the variables when they are all transformed exogenously to become endogenous at some point. This will show greater interaction among the variables and their causality effects.

- ii. An expansion of the variables and the use of Non-Linear auto-regressive distributed lag (NARDL) model analysis might produce more interesting results.

5.5 Contribution to Knowledge

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The work has contributed to knowledge by modelling military expenditure as a function of external debt using an econometric approach to

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